

A Study on the Impact of Organizational and Personal Factors on the Stress Levels of Business Education Teachers in Bangalore

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ABSTRACT

One factor common across all occupations is Stress. It is experienced when events don't happen according to what is planned or can't be managed with our ability ;it is an unpleasant emotional situation. Stress originates from the relation between a person and its environment and it exerts different impact on different persons as the same stressor can affect different individuals differently (Halkos & Bousinakis, 2010). The present study, therefore, was undertaken to find out if organizational and personal factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teachers in Bangalore. Data was collected by a well structured questionnaire which was provided to the respondents. The hypotheses were formulated based on the relationship between different variables such as stress, organisational factors, personal factors.. Based on the objectives and the nature of the collected data, appropriate statistical techniques such as analysis of variance, linear regression analysis were adopted. The findings revealed a highly significant relationship between organisational factors and stress levels and also a highly significant relationship between personal factors and stress levels.

KEYWORDS: stress, adverse effects, organisational factors, personal factors

1. INRODUCTION

The importance of teachers in the development of a country is significant. Teachers are considered as the major influence in the formative years of a student's understanding of the society. The teacher shapes the thinking of the young students (Hasan, 2014). Higher education aids in the growth of the economy of a country through knowledge sharing (Areekkuzhiyil, 2014). The merit of teachers is significant in the outreach of quality education (Chughtai and Zafar, 2006; Akhtar et al., 2008; Doctor and Ramachandran, 2008; Shibu, 2011). The approach of education is relevant in all disciplines but it is prominently felt in applied fields like management (Priyadarshini et al., 2015). The success of a university lies in its capacity of nurturing the skilled and contented faculty apart from bringing in new talents into the organisation. It is an institution that provides the next generation of work force to the nation (Adenike, 2011).

The quality of teaching includes the subject expertise, interaction and motivation of the students. In turn, the efficiency and performance of the teacher depends mostly on their job satisfaction. Research studies have shown that teachers are having huge stress bringing about decreased job satisfaction and consequently decrease in the quality of teaching. Teacher stress is defined as the negative emotions

felt by teachers such as irritation, annoyance and hopelessness due to certain aspects of their job (Kyriacou, 2001).

2. Review of literature:

Organisational causes of stress are commonly associated with the stress of the employees. Workload (Demerouti, et al., 2001; Kaur, 2007), physical environment of classes (Friesen and Williams, 1985; Harris, 2011), lower pay and incentives, duration of classes (Drago et al., 1999; Montalvo, Bair, & Boor, 1995), various other roles of teachers (Nadeem and Abbas 2009), unrestrained students (Jacobsson, Pousette, & Thylfors, 2001; Wisniewski and Gargiulo, 1997), lack of harmony with higher authorities and colleagues and high expectations are stated as the reasons for organisational stress (Rupa and Durai, 2012; Bartholomew et al., 2014; Sharma and Shakir, 2017).

Levenson (2014) determined that there was a need for harmony among colleagues for the progress of the institution. This also includes the support and knowledge sharing between them. The author explains that this is one of the roles of a teacher in an institution. **Valli and Buese (2007)** suggested that teachers need to be continuously

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aware of latest in-classroom and out-of-classroom teaching methods.

Saeed and Farooqi (2014) studied the relationship between work life balance, job stress and satisfaction among 171 university teachers from Gujrat (Pakistan). They found that there is a positive correlation between work life balance and job satisfaction implying that a harmonious balance at work and personal life provides a higher level of job satisfaction. In this study, the stress at work did not predict the job satisfaction of teachers.

Hafeez and Akbar (2015) studied the impact of work life balance on job satisfaction among elementary school teachers. They found that work-life balance factors like long working hours, work pressure, intention to change a job, flexible working conditions had no significant relationship with job satisfaction which was mainly related with salary, relationship with colleagues or management, quality family time, staff loyalty, etc. They tried to explain the independence of these two variables by putting forth current situations in Karachi like uncertain circumstances, the huge rate of inflation and smaller numbers of job opportunities, lack of application of nationwide laws etc.

3. Research Gap:

- Many studies are focused on the level of work stress among primary and secondary teachers. The research on stress among teachers from higher education level is scarce.
- Similarly different level of stress has been reported in different types of education sectors such as public, private, self-financing institute. Many studies on B-school is not yet focused.
- None of the studies incorporated the treatments or workshops/trainings to provide with coping strategies to reduce the stress thus keeping this field open for future research.

4. Objectives of the Study:

Accordingly, the main objectives of this study can be stated as follows:

- To find out organisational factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teacher in Bangalore
- To find out personal factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teacher in Bangalore.

5. Statement of the problem:

In our society, the education system is an extensive sector and the successful functioning of this sector depends on work force who are not only well educated, committed to their work but also healthy emotionally and physically. The role of a teacher is very vital for the various outcomes associated with the student and the organization. Therefore, the factors that could influence their nature have received the attention of many researchers. Stress being one of the factors has attracted much attention due to its important impact on the mental health of teachers (Sadeghi et al., 2016). What was once thought as an easy job has become stressful thanks to the nature of job, organization set up and competition for jobs in this sector. Additionally, the students who are the most important part of the education sector are also challenging the current education system. Teachers are

under pressure and are expected to learn new skills to increase and deliver the knowledge. These challenges or demands have a strong emotional effect on the teachers and impacts their performance at various levels (Kyriacou, 2001). The present study, therefore, seeks to find out if organizational and personal factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teacher in Bangalore.

6. Hypothesis:

- H1: Organisational factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teacher in Karnataka.
- H2: Personal factors have significant effect on the stress levels of business education teacher in Karnataka.

7. Research Methodology :

Explanatory and descriptive methods were used in this research study. The hypotheses were formulated based on the relationship between different variables such as stress, organisational factors, personal factors. A well structured questionnaire was prepared for the respondents. The questionnaire comprised of the following sections: demographic details, personal factors, organisational and workplace factors. Under each scale, the questionnaire consisted of different number of items and responses were scored based on Likert scale measurement. In this study, convenience sampling method was implemented. A final of 408 respondents (teachers) from different university and colleges with special reference to business schools (management and commerce discipline) in Bangalore, Karnataka were selected for this study. The data collection period was from July 2019 to November 2019. Based on the objectives and the nature of the collected data, appropriate statistical techniques such as analysis of variance, linear regression analysis were adopted.

8. Variables used in the study:

Personal Factors: measured in terms of Job Satisfaction and Work-Life Balance.

Organizational & Workplace Factors: measured in terms of Pay and Benefits, Workload, Work Relationship, Communication, Resources, Politics, and Motivation.

9. Data Analysis: Demographic factors

Data were collected from 408 university and college teachers across Bangalore working at the level of assistant professor, associate professor, professor or at a post with other responsibilities.

Stress level of the respondent

Stress is unavoidable in any profession including the teaching. In the present study, the majority of the respondents (62.5%) reported a medium level of stress in the teaching profession. This was followed by a high level of stress which 30.1% of the respondents reported. Only 7.4% of respondents reported a low level of stress implying that teaching is a stressed occupation.

Hypothesis 1: Organizational factors have a significant impact on the stress levels of business education teacher in Karnataka.

Descriptive Statistics:

Linear regression analysis was applied to study the impact of

organisational factors on the stress levels of business education teachers. The regression analysis revealed a highly significant relationship between organisational factors and

stress levels with $F=15.463$ and $p<0.05$. Thus hypothesis was accepted

Table1. Model Summary of Organizational factors Stress levels of Business Education Teacher

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.F Change
.461	0.213	0.199	0.509	0.213	15.463	7	400	0.000

Table2. Coefficients of Organizational factors Stress levels of Business Education Teacher

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.117	0.239		13.020	0.000
Pay and Benefits	-0.018	0.042	-0.024	-0.424	0.672
Workload	-0.432	0.052	-0.433	-8.331	0.000
Work Relationship	-0.149	0.070	-0.114	-2.127	0.034
Communication	0.236	0.059	0.254	4.012	0.000
Resource	0.003	0.049	0.004	0.067	0.947
Politics	0.076	0.046	0.094	1.675	0.095
Motivation	-0.020	0.041	-0.028	-0.473	0.636

Hypothesis 2: Personal factors exert a significant impact on the stress levels of business education teacher in Karnataka.

Linear regression analysis was applied to study the impact of personal factors on the stress levels of business education teachers. The regression analysis revealed a highly significant relationship between personal factors and stress levels with $F=524.2$ and $p<0.05$. The hypothesis was accepted.

Table3. Model Summary of Personal Factors Stress levels of Business Education Teacher

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.F Change
0.849	0.721	0.720	0.301	0.721	524.210	2	405	0.000

Table4. Coefficients of Personal Factors Stress levels of Business Education Teacher

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-0.619	0.101		-6.112	0.000
Mental Stress	0.010	0.028	0.011	0.358	0.721
Physical Stress	0.771	0.028	0.844	27.582	0.000

10. Conclusion:

Any employer wishes to obtain maximum productivity from his employees and this is possible when the employees give the desired result which adds value to the organization they are working in. In this study, it is found that organizational and workplace factors, and personal factors significantly impacts the stress level in business education teachers. This study has an relevance in the education sector and certain factors which create job stress among teachers have been identified taking cognizance of which institutions of higher learning may develop suitable plans to improve the efficiency of the teachers as well as the institution.

11. Limitations:

There was no direct analysis of other stress related consequences. Job Satisfaction and Work-Life Balance Pay and Benefits, Workload, Work Relationship, Communication, Resources, Politics, and Motivation have an impact on stress levels of an individual and are more specific to higher educational organizations. This study is restricted to

institutions of higher learning such as colleges and universities from commerce and management discipline in Bangalore as there are a number of recognized and registered institutions here.

12. References :

- [1] Halkos, G., & Bousinakis, D. (2010). The effect of stress and satisfaction on productivity. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 59(5), 415-431.
- [2] Hasan, A. (2014). A study of occupational stress of primary school teachers. *Educationia Confab*, 3(4), 11-19.
- [3] Areekkuzhiyil, S. (2014). Factors Influencing the Organizational Stress among Teachers Working in Higher Education Sector in Kerala: An Empirical Analysis. *Research and Pedagogic Interventions*, 2(2).
- [4] Chughtai, A.A. and Zafar, S. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of organizational commitment among

- Pakistani University teachers. *Applied H.R.M. Research*, 11(1), 39-64.
- [5] Akhtar, I., Muniruddin, G., & Sogra, K.J (2008). A trend analysis of faculty turnover at the private universities in Bangladesh: A business school perspective. *Journal of Business Studies*, 4(1), 139-151.
- [6] Doctor, G., & Ramachandran, S. (2008). DSpace@ IBSA: knowledge sharing in a management institute. *Vine*, 38(1), 42-52.
- [7] Shibu, N.S. (2011) 'Job satisfaction of faculty members of private engineering colleges – in context of Tamilnadu, India', *Global Journal of Finance and Management*, 3(1), 1-13.
- [8] Priyadarshini, C., Ponnamp, A., & Banerjee, P. (2015). Role stress and coping among business school professors: A phenomenological study. *The Qualitative Report*, 20(12), 2050-2066.
- [9] Adenike, A. (2011). Organizational climate as a predictor of employee job satisfaction: Evidence from Covenant University. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 4(1), 151-166.
- [10] Kyriacou, C. (2001). Teacher stress: Directions for future research. *Educational review*, 53(1), 27-35.
- [11] Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 86(3), 499.
- [12] Kaur, H. (2007). Mental health of Post Graduate Students in relation to their Value-Conflict. M.Ed. Dissertation, Punjab University.
- [13] Drago, R., Caplan, R., Constanza, D., & Brubaker, T. (1999). New estimates of working time for elementary school teachers. *Monthly Lab. Rev.*, 122, 31-38.
- [14] Montalvo, A., Bair, J. H., & Boor, M. (1995). Teachers' perceptions of occupational stress factors. *Psychological Reports*, 76(3), 846-846.
- [15] Nadeem, M. S., & Abbas, Q. (2009). The impact of work life conflict on job satisfactions of employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 63-83.
- [16] Jacobsson, C., Pousette, A., & Thylefors, I. (2001). Managing stress and feelings of mastery among Swedish comprehensive school teachers. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 45(1), 37-53.
- [17] Wisniewski, L., & Gargiulo, R. M. (1997). Occupational stress and burnout among special educators: A review of the literature. *The Journal of special education*, 31(3), 325-346.
- [18] Rupa, J., & Durai, V. (2012). A Study on Stress Among School Teachers with Special Reference to Madurai District. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.2115412.
- [19] Sharma, S., & Shakir, M. (2017). Stress management among teachers: The Bhagavad Gita's approach. *Educational Quest: An International Journal of Education and Applied Social Sciences*, 8(2), 671.
- [20] Levenson, M. R. (2014). *Pathways to Teacher Leadership: Emerging Models, Changing Roles*. Harvard Education Press, Cambridge.
- [21] Valli, L., & Buese, D. (2007). The changing roles of teachers in an era of high-stakes accountability. *American Educational Research Journal*, 44(3), 519-558.
- [22] Saeed, K., & Farooqi, Y. A. (2014). Examining the relationship between work life balance, job stress, and job satisfaction among university teachers (A case of University of Gujarat). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences and Engineering*, 5(6), 9-15.
- [23] Hafeez, U., & Akbar, W. (2015). Impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction among school teachers of 21st century. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 4(11), 25-37.
- [24] Sadeghi, A., Niyafar, G. H., Pour, A. H., Zamani, A., & Gholami, F. (2016). Relationship between Personality Types and Job Stress among Teachers at First Period (Guidance Schools) and Second Period of High School (Secondary Schools). *Creative Education*, 7(03), 544.